

EFFECT OF EXTREME TEMPERATURE CYCLES ON DAMAGE IN COMPOSITE LAMINATES

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1 Introduction

Materials used in aerospace applications undergo important temperature variations in service. Because of the difference between the coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) of the matrix and the fiber, significant stresses are induced in the laminate. Those stresses can produce microcracking and cause deterioration of the laminate mechanical properties. Also, microcracks can affect the thermal stability of the laminate by changing the CTE. Therefore, it is important to study the behavior of the laminate under these temperature variations.

Previous works have shown that thermal cycling can induce changes in the composite mechanical properties. Gao et al. [1] have observed a diminution of tensile strength in the 0°- and 90°- directions of a carbon/epoxy unidirectional laminate after only a few thermal cycles. Kim et al. [2] have shown that the CTE of carbon/epoxy cross-ply laminate changes with the presence of transverse microcracks induced by mechanical loading or thermal loading.

Studies were also conducted to characterize the damage state of the composite materials due to thermal cycles [3-7]. Microscopic observation is a widely used technique to characterize damage. Research works have demonstrated that damage observed on the edge of a sample, are not necessary representative of damages found in the middle of it [3, 5, 6, 7]. However, it is not possible to conclude from those researches if damage inside a laminate is more important than on the edges, since results change according to the study. Furthermore, studies have shown a great variation in the damage types that were observed according to the materials systems and stacking sequences used for the laminates [3-7].

In this study, the effects of thermal cycling on damage in carbon/cyanate ester laminates are investigated. Microscopic observations are used to evaluate the damage state of the laminates first on the edges and then in the middle.

2 Experimental work

2.1 Materials

The material used in this study is a five-harness carbon fiber satin weave textile impregnated with cyanate ester resin. Two lay-up sequences were studied: Laminate A $[0/0^*/0/0^*]_S$ and Laminate B $[0/45/45^*/0^*]_{2S}$. The asterisk refers to a ply that is flipped.

2.2 Thermo-cycling

Prior to thermal cycling, two specimens of Laminate A and three of Laminate B were polished on one edge as shown in Figure 1. Those samples were cycled with others samples from Laminates A and B. The others samples were used to determine the damage state inside the laminates.

Thermal cycling was performed in an environmental chamber. As shown in Figure 2, the thermal cycle starts at room temperature. The chamber temperature increases to 145 °C with an average rate of 13 °C/min.

Fig. 1 Polished edges of laminates A and B

Once the temperature reaches 145°C, it stays there for ten minutes. Then, the temperature decreases to -170°C with an average rate of 19°C/min. After 10 minutes, at -170°C, the temperature goes back to room temperature and the cycle starts again. During the thermal cycles, the humidity is kept under 10%. The number of cycles for each series of thermal cycles was predetermined and all of the polished samples were observed using an optical microscope after each series. At the end, 160 thermal cycles were performed on the samples.

2.3 Microscopic observation of damage on edges

The polished edges of the five specimens shown in Figure 1 were observed after each series of cycles. As shown in Figure 3, two types of damage were visible: transverse microcracks and debonding between the fibers and the matrix on the perimeter of the yarn. Both types of damage were quantified on an area of one centimeter-long by the thickness of the laminate after each series of cycles, in order to establish the evolution of damage according to the number of cycles performed.

Matrix transverse cracks

Figures 4 and 5 present the evolution of the number of transverse cracks with the number of thermal cycles for the five specimens. The number of microcracks was established in the following manner. A crack was counted as one when its length was about one yarn thickness.

When the crack length was about half the yarn thickness, it was counted as ½. When the crack length was less than half the yarn thickness, it was not accounted for.

Fig. 2 Thermal cycle definition

The number of cracks has been quantified in the outer and in the inner plies. The sum of the two numbers gives the total number of cracks in the observed section. The outer plies are defined as the first and last plies for Laminate A. For Laminate B, they are defined as the first and last three plies.

In the 0°-direction of laminate A (Figure 4a), transverse cracks initiate after only one cycle. The number of cracks keeps increasing with the number of cycles. However, the number of cracks in the outer plies seems to reach a plateau around 20 cycles. After 20 cycles, damage continues growing but it is essentially in the inner layers of the laminate.

Similar results are obtained for the 90°-direction of Laminate A as observed in Figure 4b. However, the extent of microcracking is much more severe than in the 0°-direction. After 160 cycles, the number of cracks is about twice the number of cracks in the 0°-direction.

Figure 5 shows the results obtained for Laminate B along the 0°-, 90°-, and 45°- directions. Cracks initiate after only a few cycles and continue appearing and growing after 160 cycles in the inner and outer plies. The extent of microcracks is more severe in the outer plies than in the inner plies. It is also more severe in the 0°-direction than in the 90°- and 45°- directions.

Matrix-yarn debonding

Interfacial debonding between the fibers and the matrix was studied for the five specimens.

Fig. 3 Microscopic observation of damage in the laminate

Only debonding of the yarns perpendicular to the observed section are visible on the micrographs. The extent of debonding was evaluated using the following methodology. The number of yarns perpendicular to the section was counted over the observed area (1 cm x laminate thickness). After each series of cycles, the number of yarns subjected to debonding was determined and the extent of debonding of each yarn was evaluated in percentage. Finally, the number of damaged yarns was divided by the total number of yarns to obtain a percentage of damaged yarns. Since the interfacial debonding evolution was observed to be similar through the laminate thickness, no distinction is made in the results between the outer plies and in the inner plies.

Figures 6 and 7 present the evolution of the percentage of damaged yarns with the number of thermal cycles for the five specimens. Four levels of debonding extent are presented: 25%, 50%, 75% and 100%. Debonding extent starts to be rated when a quarter of the yarn perimeter is debonded from the matrix. This corresponds to a level of 25%.

Fig. 4 Development of microcracks in Laminate A as a function of thermal cycles number: a) along the 0°-direction. b) along the 90°-direction

As interfacial debonding grows and reaches half of the yarn perimeter, debonding extent is rated as being 50%. The damaged yarn is however not deducted from the 25% level. The same calculation is done as debonding extent reaches 75% and 100%. Therefore, a yarn which is entirely debonded is accounted at four levels, i.e., 100%, 75%, 50% and 25%. The calculation method allows having data points that keep on increasing for each debonding level extent. That way, it is easier to follow interfacial debonding growth.

Fig. 5 Development of microcracks in Laminate B as a function of thermal cycles number: a) along the 0°-direction, b) along the 90°-direction, c) along the 45°-direction

The total number of yarns that present some interfacial debonding, regardless of the extent and that have been counted, is also represented in the figures.

For Laminate A, the percentage of yarns subjected to interfacial debonding is shown in Figure 6. Interfacial debonding initiates after one cycle and grows very rapidly.

Along the 0°-direction (Fig. 6a), after only one cycle 68% of the yarns are subjected to some interfacial debonding, but the extent is limited. Only about 11% of the yarns are debonded over 50% of their perimeter. After 50 cycles, 100% of the yarns exhibit interfacial debonding, but the extent varies from a few fibers to the entire yarn perimeter. About 83% of the yarns are debonded over at least 25% of their perimeter. After 160 cycles, about 93% of the yarns are debonded over at least 25% of their perimeter and about 5% are entirely debonded.

Along the 90°-direction (Fig. 6b), after only one cycle, 60% of the yarns are subjected to some interfacial debonding, but the extent is limited. Only about 7% of the yarns are debonded over 50% of their perimeter. After 40 cycles, 100% of the yarns exhibit interfacial debonding, but the extent varies from a few fibers to the entire yarn perimeter. About 90% of the yarns are debonded over at least 25% of their perimeter. After 160 cycles, about 97% of the yarns are debonded over at least 25% of their perimeter and about 9% are entirely debonded.

For Laminate B, the percentage of yarns subjected to interfacial debonding is shown in Figure 7. As for Laminate A, interfacial debonding initiates during the first cycle and grows very rapidly.

Along the 0°-direction (Fig. 7a), 46% of the yarns show some interfacial debonding after one cycle. The number increases to 98% after 50 cycles. Among them, about 60% have debonding over at least 25% of the perimeter. After 160 cycles, about 78% of the yarns are debonded over at least 25% of their perimeter and about 1.3% of them are entirely debonded.

Along the 90°-direction (Fig. 7b), 30% of the yarns show some interfacial debonding after one cycle.

The number increases to 96% after 50 cycles. Among them, about 44% show debonding over at least 25% of the perimeter. After 160 cycles, about 74% of the yarns are debonded over at least 25% of their perimeter, but no yarn is entirely debonded.

Along the 45°-direction (Fig. 7c), about 24% of the yarns show some interfacial debonding after one cycle. The number increases to 100% after 50 cycles. Among them, about 73% have debonding over at least 25% of the perimeter. After 160 cycles, about 87% of the yarns are debonded over at least 25% of their perimeter, but no yarn is entirely debonded.

Discussion

Laminate A and Laminate B both show microcracks and interfacial debonding on the external edges after only one thermal cycle. However, the microcracks are more abundant in the cross-ply laminate than in the quasi-isotropic laminate.

Fig. 6 Development of fiber-matrix debonding in Laminate A as a function of thermal cycles number: a) Along the 0°-direction, b) Along the 90°-direction

Debonding is quite predominant for both laminates. After 50 cycles, almost all yarns in the area of observation are partially touched.

2.4 Damage in the laminate

Many studies have demonstrated that damage observed inside the specimen is not necessarily the same on the edges.

Fig. 7 Development of fiber-matrix debonding in Laminate B as a function of thermal cycles number: a) along the 0°-direction, b) along the 90°-direction, c) along the 45°-direction

Therefore, the investigation of damage inside the specimen is an important part in determining the laminate damage state.

Methodology

Samples of Laminates A and B were cycled 160 times. They were then embedded in resin, cut and polished. Although cutting the embedded specimen with a saw may induce damage on the surface of the cut cross-section, it is completely removed by polishing. The cut was made in the middle of the specimen as shown in Figure 8. The area of observation is at a distance of 12.5 mm from the edge. Microscopic observations are made along the 0°-direction of the laminate.

Result for Laminate A

Figure 9 shows a micrograph of the cut cross-section of Laminate A after 160 cycles. There are numerous transverse microcracks in the inner and outer plies. However, interfacial debonding is not visible as it was the case on the laminate edges.

Figure 10 shows a comparison between the number of microcracks on the edge and in the middle of the specimen for Laminate A. The number of microcracks decreases to approximately half of the quantity observed on the edge. The diminution is more important for the inner plies than for the outer plies. The number of cracks decreases from 71 on the edge to 35.5 in the middle for the inner plies. For the outer plies, the number decreases from 90 on the edge to 55.5 in the middle. Although the number of microcracks has decreased, this damage mode is still very present in the laminate.

Fig. 8 Area of microscopic observations for Laminates A and B

Result for Laminate B

As for Laminate A, the microscopic images of Laminate B show transverse cracks but no debonding between the fiber and the matrix. However, for Laminate B, there is a significant difference between the observations on the edge and the observations on the middle cross-section of the specimen. The total number of microcracks observed on the edge is 116.5 in comparison with 15.5 on the middle cross-section of the specimen as shown in Figure 11. The most significant difference is for the outer plies. The number of microcracks observed decreases from 79 on the edge to 8.5 in the middle.

2.5 Edge effects

The microscopic observations in the middle of the sample show no interfacial debonding, which tends to demonstrate that interfacial debonding seen on the edge of the samples is mainly due to edge effect phenomenon. Edge effects are therefore studied in this section.

Methodology

In order to validate this hypothesis, a sample of Laminate A was used. The sample was polished before being cycled up to 160 thermal cycles. Microscopic observations were done on the edge of the sample along the 0°-direction. The sample was polished a second time on the same edge to remove approximately 0.2 mm of material and the edge was observed again with a microscope.

Fig. 9 Inside of Laminate A in the 0°-direction after 160 cycles

The sample was polished further to be 1 mm away from the initial external edge. Microscopic observations were performed another time. Those observations were made qualitatively in order to evaluate the presence of interfacial debonding away from the edge of the specimen and the evolution of transverse cracks.

Fig. 10 Comparison of the number of microcracks in Laminate A on the edge and in the middle of the specimen after 160 cycles

Fig. 11 Comparison of the number of microcracks in Laminate B on the edge and in the middle of the specimen after 160 cycles

Results

Figure 12 shows a micrograph of the laminate external edge (a) and a micrograph of a cross-section 0.2 mm away from the laminate edge (b). A comparison of the two micrographs allows studying the evolution of the damage state in the specimen.

It can be observed that the microcracks present in (a) are still visible in (b). The microcracks have propagated inside the laminate. Interfacial debonding is clearly visible in Figure 12a but is not visible anymore after removing 0.2 mm of material (Figure 12b).

One millimeter away from the edge, the damage state is similar to the one observed 0.2 mm away from the edge. No interfacial debonding is present but a large number of transverse microcracks are still visible in the inner and outer plies.

3. Conclusions

In this study, damage induced by thermal cycling in laminates reinforced with a five-harness carbon fiber satin weave textile and impregnated with cyanate ester resin was investigated.

(a) Damage state on the edge of the specimen

(b) Damage state 0.2 mm away from the specimen edge

Fig. 12 : Damage state of Laminate A after 160 cycles: edge effect study

Two stacking sequences were studied: Laminate A $[0/0^*/0/0^*]_S$ and Laminate B $[0/45/45^*/0^*]_{2S}$. The asterisk refers to a ply that is flipped.

Microscopic observations were used to evaluate the damage state of the laminate first on the external edges and then in the middle.

On the external edges, two types of damage were visible, i.e., microcracks and interfacial debonding. Both types of damage appear after one cycle and increase quite rapidly. Microcracks in the outer plies grow faster than in the inner plies. After about 50 cycles, all yarns are subjected to interfacial debonding which extent varies from a few fibers to a complete yarn perimeter.

In the middle of the samples, damage was observed to be quite different from the external edges. Microcracks were not as abundant, especially for the quasi-isotropic laminate. Interfacial debonding was not visible anymore. This damage mode seems to be due to edge effects.

To explore this hypothesis further, a sample which had been polished on the edge and subjected to 160 thermal cycles was polished further to remove more material. The micrographs showed that only microcracks were visible at 0.2 mm away from the external edge. This observation reinforces the assumption that interfacial debonding is caused by edge effects.

In order to fully determine the damage state of Laminates A and B after 160 cycles, the evolution of transverse microcracks will be study through the width of the laminates. The numbers of microcracks will be evaluated at specific distances from the edge until the full coverage of the specimen will be done.

Once the evolution of the damage state is determined in Laminates A and B, the next step is to evaluate the influence of those damages on the mechanical behavior of both laminates. Tensile tests, in-plane shear tests and in-plane thermal expansion tests will be conducted. Short beam shear tests will also be performed to characterize the evolution of interlaminar shear strength.

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